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Assessing The Relationship Between Socioeconomic Status And Psychological Well-Being Among University Students During An Economic Crisis In Sri Lanka

Asma Banu Riyaz

Department of Psychology, International College of Business and Technology (ICBT Campus), Sri Lanka,
affiliated with Cardiff Metropolitan University, (UK)

Email: asmariyaz15@gmail.com

Abstract

University students in Sri Lanka have been adversely affected by the country's economic crisis due to inadequate economic and student resources, contributing to poorer psychological well-being. This study sought to examine the relationship between socioeconomic status and psychological well-being among university students amid the economic crisis in Sri Lanka. The sample consisted of 97 university students who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and were obtained through convenience sampling. Data collection was conducted through a self-administered questionnaire conducted via Qualtrics. Psychological well-being (Depression, anxiety, and stress) was examined using the DASS-21, while socioeconomic status was determined using the Family Affluence Scale and a Likert-scale question measuring monthly household income. Further, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to determine the direction and significance of the relationship between socioeconomic status and psychological well-being. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess significant differences in the mean scores of depression, anxiety, and stress across classes of income. Findings revealed a non-significant negative correlation between socioeconomic status and psychological well-being, and university students belonging to the middle socioeconomic status had greater levels of depression, anxiety, and stress during the economic crisis. These findings contribute to a broader understanding of how the two variables' association is complex and multifactorial, providing an alternative perspective to previous findings. Recommendations for future research are provided.

Keywords; socioeconomic status, psychological well-being, university students, economic crisis

Introduction

The government of Sri Lanka declared the worst economic collapse the country has experienced in the last seventy-three years. The country was in a critical situation due to poor economic governance, a rise in foreign debt, a drop in international reserves and soaring inflation (Kumar et al., 2023; O' Neill, 2023). Additionally, the Easter Sunday bombings and the COVID-19 pandemic aggravated the crisis (Shoib et al., 2022). The heightened pressure of the crisis led to mass public protests, creating a weak political administration, which had a significant impact on the economic decline (Vivekanantharasa & Blanco, 2022).

The education system that operates as a major catalyst to Sri Lanka's economic growth failed to fulfil the needs of the student population (Raveenthiran, 2022). Nearly 4.3 million students were impacted due to the shortage of necessary resources (Raveenthiran, 2022). The fuel crisis and the significant surge in transportation expenses (Vivekanantharasa & Blanco, 2022) hindered students and educators' access to their educational institutions (Raveenthiran, 2022). As a result, all educational institutions were forced to suspend physical classes and shift to virtual learning. However, lower-middle-class families, notably those in remote areas, were adversely impacted, with over 70% of students facing difficulties due to inconsistent power supply and inadequate access to internet services and suitable electronic devices (Shoib et al., 2022; Vivekanantharasa & Blanco, 2022)

University students, particularly, are vulnerable to stress due to the transition into adulthood and the academically and psychologically demanding nature of university life (Kessler, 2023; Saleem et al., 2013). Besides, the economic crisis has contributed to the

deterioration of psychological well-being (PW) among university students. The Conservation of Resources Theory serves as a theoretical basis for examining the implications of economic crises on university students' PW. The theory suggests that psychological distress occurs when individuals experience reduced access to essential resources, including financial stability, social support, and psychological resilience (Farkash et al., 2022). Similarly, during an economic crisis, university students often face financial challenges through escalating living expenses and tuition fees (Vivekanantharasa & Blanco, 2022). Institutional cost-reduction strategies, including overcrowded class sizes, limited course options, and inadequate student assistance, could exacerbate student distress. In addition, reduced employment prospects along with a saturated labour market can increase concerns regarding long-term employability (Stein et al., 2013). Together, these challenges may weaken resilience and impair university students' PW.

Psychological Well-being among University Students

PW is generally associated with positive emotional states such as subjective happiness and optimal functioning across different areas of life (Deci & Ryan, 2008). It is also characterized by the degree of perceived control individuals have over their life circumstances and interests (Udhayakumar & Illango, 2018). However, PW among university students has been worsening in recent years due to growing demands arising from the rising complexity of present-day life (Mahees, 2020), and a large body of research has emphasized the gravity of these challenges. For instance, research involving 1,850 university students found that approximately one-third had an identifiable psychological condition, while one-fourth of newly admitted students

experienced distress and sought professional support (Saleem et al., 2013). These findings indicate that the adaptation phase into university life represents a highly critical period during which students are more prone to experience psychological distress.

In this study, psychological well-being is conceptualised in terms of psychological distress, where symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress are used as indicators, with higher levels reflecting poorer psychological well-being and lower levels indicating better psychological well-being among university students.

Stress

The World Health Organisation (2020) defines stress as a state that emerges when environmental demands surpass an individual's abilities or knowledge, thereby impairing their coping mechanisms. Stress is a widely experienced condition among university students, particularly in Sri Lanka (Madhusanka et al., 2021; Mahees, 2020). This is largely due to the intense competition for admission to government universities, which results from limited university placements and overcrowded conditions. Furthermore, students' stress levels may also be influenced by their socioeconomic status (SES) and their inability to pursue their preferred field of study because of parents' traditionally high expectations to enter prestigious professional careers such as medicine, engineering, or law, due to the associated social status and employment opportunities (Wanigasinghe & Rathnayaka, 2019). These factors significantly contribute to elevated stress levels among students, consequently increasing their vulnerability to mental health problems. In particular, chronic stress heightens the risk of anxiety and increases

the likelihood of anxiety developing into a disorder.

Anxiety

Anxiety is a common response that individuals project when they feel anxious and stressed about what to expect. It's a psychological state characterized by feelings of tension, worry, and apprehension about anticipated events or uncertain outcomes. It may manifest across cognitive, physical, and behavioural domains (American Psychological Association [APA], 2022).

Among university students, anxiety has been associated with multiple academic and psychosocial factors. A study reported that approximately 29% of the student population experienced symptoms of anxiety. The study highlighted that the academic year, financial difficulties, substance use, sleep quality, health and weight index, social engagement, uncertainty about the future, interpersonal conflicts with students and lecturers were identified to be the risk factors for anxiety among university students (Mohamad et al., 2021).

Depression

Depression is the most widespread disorder that affects 280 million people globally (Wickramasinghe et al., 2023). It is characterized by prolonged feelings of intense despair, which hinders an individual's capacity to function in their daily life. People suffering from depression may face challenges in concentration, experience reduced self-worth, or persistent guilt, as well as in some critical cases, recurring thoughts of self-harm or suicidal behavior (APA, 2022).

Evidence on the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among university students shows considerable variation across contexts. Several studies report relatively high levels of psychological distress, with a meta-analytic evidence among Chinese university students with a prevalence rate of depression and anxiety at 24% and 22% respectively (Zhang et al., 2021). Similarly, studies among Pakistani (Asif et al., 2020) and Bangladeshi (Hossain et al., 2022) university students found notable levels of depression, anxiety and stress, with anxiety often emerging as the dominant condition. However, an Indian study highlighted that depression was the dominant disorder, with anxiety and stress also reported at notably high levels among university students (Raja et al., 2022).

In contrast, other studies report comparatively lower or moderate prevalence rates, such as findings from Spanish university students, where stress, depression and anxiety were moderately reported (Ramón-Arbués et al., 2020). Although the study used a reliable measure, the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21), the findings may not be generalizable due to the sample being limited to a private college, where students may have had greater socioeconomic advantages and access to supportive academic environments that could reduce psychological distress. In addition, studies conducted among healthcare students in Sri Lanka (Gamage et al., 2021) and Jordan (Basheti et al., 2021) reported generally normal levels of psychological distress. The Sri Lankan study identified normal levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, whereas the Jordanian study reported normal levels of depression and anxiety only. These variations in anxiety, stress, and depression levels could be attributed to the application of vast knowledge

of physical health, mental health, and lifestyle that has contributed to better PW.

Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status (SES) is one of the essential components that has a major influence on youth PW (Lal et al., 2013). Typically, SES is an indicator of a person's or family's social standing based on their household income, educational background, and employment status (Saifi & Mehmood, 2011). These three factors are commonly identified as the key indicators of SES. However, income levels may have a more direct effect on the PW of university students, as they determine access to financial and psychological support services. For instance, one of the key challenges identified in a study exploring help-seeking behaviours among university students for mental health concerns was the "lack of money" (Chandrasekara, 2020), highlighting that financial stability may influence students' ability to seek therapy and support services. Additionally, previous Sri Lankan studies (Rathnayake & Weerahewa, 2005; Thoradeniya et al., 2006) have also used income levels alone to measure SES among participants. Therefore, although other SES indicators may influence PW, this study specifically focused solely on income levels as an indicator of SES.

Socioeconomic Status and Psychological Well-being

Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the associations between SES and PW among university students. Studies by Mohammad et al. (2020), Saleem et al. (2013), and Wahed & Hassan (2017) reported a negative correlation between SES and PW. While the studies had a considerably large sample size, ensuring reliability, a drawback of the studies was their dependence on self-report measures,

which may have introduced response bias. Nevertheless, these studies validate the understanding that students from lower SES experience increased PW issues.

Although a substantial body of literature demonstrates that lower SES is linked with poorer PW, the findings remain inconsistent across several studies. Multiple studies report higher depressive symptoms among lower SES students, with results varying from slight increases above normal levels (Mohammad et al., 2020) to moderate levels of depression (Ibrahim et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2013). However, these findings should be considered carefully, as some studies present methodological limitations that may limit comparison across studies. For example, Ibrahim et al. (2012) study participants were based on a single university, raising concerns regarding generalizability, while Chen et al. (2013) included an uneven small sample of low SES participants, which could have shaped the results outcomes. Conversely, other studies did not show a consistent link between SES and PW issues. For instance, Shamsuddin et al. (2013) found no statistically significant relationship between family income and depression or anxiety, except for stress among lower SES groups. Similarly, mixed findings have been found in which psychological distress is higher among middle SES students (Agberotimi et al., 2020), while other evidence indicates increased depression and anxiety among higher SES groups (Salami & Walker, 2014). The above diverse studies suggest that the relationship between SES and PW is multifaceted and inconsistent across contexts, indicating that PW outcomes are likely influenced by a combination of contextual and psychosocial factors apart from SES alone

These studies provide a perspective into how PW varies across socioeconomic groups among university students. However, there has been limited research investigating the relationship between SES and PW among university students in Sri Lanka during an economic crisis, underscoring a gap in the literature. While multiple studies have investigated the psychological impacts of academic and developmental demands on university students, it is equally important to examine wider living circumstances that may contribute negatively to students' PW (Reiss et al., 2019).

One such wider living circumstance is the economic crisis currently experienced in Sri Lanka. Economic crises create multiple economic and social pressures that may place students at risk of developing psychological problems. This is particularly important in the university context, as the demand for higher education tends to remain high during periods of economic instability due to the perception that obtaining a degree may secure better living conditions (Varghese, 2001). Consequently, students may continue pursuing higher education despite experiencing significant financial and psychological pressures, potentially affecting their PW

Furthermore, although low- and middle-income countries are among the most disproportionately affected during economic crises, relatively insufficient research has been conducted within these contexts (Frasquilho et al., 2016). Sri Lanka, as a lower-middle-income country currently experiencing a severe economic crisis, therefore deserves particular consideration. The prevailing crisis is likely affecting individuals across different socioeconomic groups, which may subsequently impact the PW of university students. Therefore, this study attempted to investigate which socioeconomic category of

university students experienced higher psychological distress during the prevailing economic crisis in Sri Lanka.

The Current Study

This study sought to contribute to the existing literature by examining the association between SES and PW among university students amid an economic crisis in Sri Lanka. The research hypothesised that;

(H₁) There is a positive relationship between PW and SES, with higher SES associated with higher levels of PW.

(H₂) Sri Lankan university students belonging to the low SES face greater psychological wellbeing issues during an economic crisis.

Methodology

Design

The research utilised a quantitative cross-sectional correlational design to investigate if there was a significant connection between SES and PW. The research methodology facilitated establishing the direction and strength of the association between SES and PW as well as evaluating and confirming the hypotheses of the study. In addition, comparative analyses were conducted to examine differences in psychological well-being across socioeconomic groups. The independent variable was SES, operationalised using two indicators: the Family Affluence Scale (FAS) and a self-reported monthly household income scale categorising participants into lower-, middle-, and upper-income groups. The dependent variable was psychological well-being (PW), assessed through levels of psychological distress, including anxiety, depression, and stress. The study was conducted in the form of a self-report survey in Qualtrics,

lasting approximately 5-10 minutes. Surveys were chosen to gather data as they are quite efficient in reaching the target population faster than other approaches. Data was analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics (version 29.0.1.0) (IBM Corp, 2021). The protocol was approved by the Cardiff School of Sport and Health Sciences Ethics Committee (Reference No. UG-7494) in accordance with the Cardiff Metropolitan University Ethics Policy and the Declaration of Helsinki.

Sample

The study required a minimum sample size of 113 Sri Lankan university students as per the analyses of G power software for both linear bivariate regression (medium effect and power value 0.95) and Multivariate Analysis of Variance (medium effect size and power value 0.80) (Faul, et al., 2009). Convenience sampling was used to select participants based on availability, as it was a quick and efficient method of data collection. The study was advertised through a social media advert titled “Assessing the Relationship between Socioeconomic Status and Psychological Well-being among university students.” The eligibility criteria were that participants needed to be 18 years or older, be enrolled in a Sri Lankan university, and have the ability to comprehend the English language to participate in the study.

A total of 166 university students attempted the survey. But sixty-six incomplete and one incorrect response were eliminated to maintain data accuracy, avoiding imputation methods. Additionally, two responses were excluded for not meeting the requirements (participants under 18 years of age). Consequently, the study included 97 participant responses in the analysis, all of whom rigorously satisfied the established

criteria. Despite a slightly reduced sample size, this thorough data validation shows the dataset's quality, assuring substantial and meaningful insights.

Procedure

The social media advert of the study consisted of the QR code as well as a link to access the survey. Additionally, the term “during an economic crisis,” from the title of the study was removed from the social media advert to avoid participant bias as the term itself can lead the participants to report lower levels of well-being. Upon accessing the survey through a link or the code, participants were provided with an information sheet and a consent form and were also given the option to download them. Informed Consent of the participants was obtained using a tick box question before commencing the study. Subsequently, participants completed the demographics questionnaire, DASS-21, and the SES measures which included the FAS scale, and a Likert scale question related to income levels. At the conclusion of the study, participants were thanked for their involvement.

Materials

DASS-21 : DASS-21 (a 21-item self-reporting questionnaire) was used to evaluate the symptom severity of the sub-scales of depression ($\alpha = .83$), anxiety ($\alpha = .79$), and stress ($\alpha = .79$). The overall scale reliability was $\alpha = .91$. For each statement such as “I found it difficult to relax,” participants were instructed to evaluate their symptoms using a 0–3 scale, where 0 indicated that the item had not applied to them at all over the previous week and 3 indicated that it had applied very much or for most of that week. The scores filled under each subset were calculated and multiplied by two, as DASS-21 is a condensed version of DASS-42.

For depression, anxiety, and stress, the normal score varied from 0 to 9, 0 to 7, and 0 to 14, while the maximum score varied from 10 to 28, 8 to 20, and 15 to 34, respectively.

SES Measures: SES was operationalised using two indicators depending on the objective of the analysis. For correlational analyses (Hypothesis 1), SES was measured using the Family Affluence Scale (FAS), which provided a continuous indicator of socioeconomic status. For comparative group analyses (Hypothesis 2), participants were categorised into low-, middle-, and high-income groups based on self-reported household income obtained through a demographic questionnaire.

The FAS was employed to assess a family's socioeconomic status by measuring their wealth. The scale comprised of six items of the following; ownership of a family vehicle (No = 0; Yes, one = 1; Yes, two = 2), own bedroom (No = 0; Yes = 1), family computers (None = 0, One = 1; Two = 2; More than two = 3), bathrooms (None = 0; One = 1; Two = 2; More than two = 3), dishwasher (No = 0; Yes = 1) and Family holidays outside the country during the past 12 months (Never = 0; Once = 1; Twice = 2; More than twice = 3). The affluence level is calculated after each indicator is combined; higher scores represent greater material wealth and affluence, and lower scores represent decreased material wealth and affluence (Chzhen et al., 2016). The overall scale reliability was $\alpha = .55$

Besides, the Likert scale question measured the monthly household income of the participants. The participants were requested to select a range from 5 options, such as ‘between Rs. 72,001 – Rs. 103,000’, that best represents their monthly household income. These options ranged from the upper class to the lower class. Each range represented an SES. For instance, less than Rs.

48,000 was classified as lower class, and between Rs. 48,001 to Rs. 72,000 was classified as upper lower class, and similar income range categorisations were applied to lower middle class, upper middle class, and upper class. The levels of income were evaluated based on the data provided by the Department of Census and Statistics (2019). The study applied the inflation-adjusted income equation to convert the income levels from 2019 to those of 2022 by incorporating the inflation rates. Ultimately, the amounts were rounded to the closest thousand.

Ethical Consideration

Participants were provided with a consent form and an information sheet that outlined the study aims, inclusion criteria, right to withdraw, confidentiality, anonymity, risks, and the benefits of participating in the study. The information sheet also mentioned the right to withdraw at any given point during the study by exiting the browser, except after submitting the responses, as the extraction of that specific data would be impossible due to the anonymity of the data. Additionally, the confidentiality of the responses provided by the participants was assured and was stored in a password-protected OneDrive folder, which will be destroyed 10 years after project completion. Further participants in this study were provided with referral pathways to seek professional mental health support if the need emerged as a result of their participation. In addition, the email addresses of the study investigators were also presented if the participants required further assistance.

Analysis & Results

Data was exported from Qualtrics after data collection and entered into SPSS software for analysis. Data was cleaned by removing redundant columns (start date, end date, IP

address, and so on), incomplete responses, incorrect responses (wherein a respondent replaced their name with an age), and those that did not meet the study criteria. Further, numerical values were already assigned for each scale point when exporting data to SPSS, and certain variables were renamed for clarity purposes.

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis was computed to present demographic characteristics. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 49 years, with a mean age of 24.56 years ($SD = 5.84$) The distribution was positively skewed, with the majority of participants (58.8%) falling between 18 and 23 years of age, reflecting a predominantly young adult sample. In terms of gender, the sample was predominantly female, with 71 participants identifying as female (73.2%), 24 as male (24.7%), and 2 identifying as other (2.1%). With regard to educational qualification, the most common level of education was bachelor's degree ($n = 44, 45.4\%$), followed by Diploma ($n = 34, 35.1\%$), master's degree ($n = 13, 13.4\%$), Certificate ($n = 3, 3.1\%$), Postgraduate studies ($n = 2, 2.1\%$), and PhD ($n = 1, 1.0\%$).

Additionally, a reliability analysis was also conducted to check the reliability of the scales, with the DASS-21 demonstrating excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .910$) and the FAS yielding a comparatively lower reliability coefficient ($\alpha = .548$).

Psychological well-being among university students

The sub-scales of DASS-21 (depression, anxiety, and stress) were computed into three new variables, where the scores were summed up and multiplied by two and were categorised based on the severity level. The descriptive analysis of depression (Figure 1), anxiety (Figure 2), and

stress (Figure 3) scores was conducted to demonstrate the severity distribution of psychological well-being among university students.

Figure 1: *Severity Distribution of Depression among University Students*

Figure 2: *Severity Distribution of Anxiety among University Students*

Figure 3: *Severity Distribution of Stress among University Students*

Socioeconomic classes of the university students

To make subsequent analyses and referencing more convenient, the study recorded the initial five SES classes in the SES Likert scale on household income into two new variables. For instance, combining 'lower class' and 'upper lower class' as 'low SES' and combining the 'upper middle class' and 'upper classes as 'high SES.' The descriptive analysis demonstrated that the majority of the participants belonged to the lower-income class ($n=37$), while an equal number of participants in the study belonged to the middle ($n=30$) and high-income classes ($n=30$).

Inferential analysis

The mean scores for the FAS, DASS-21 scale, and the subsets depression, anxiety, and stress were calculated for subsequent analysis.

Relationship between psychological well-being and socioeconomic status

To test H_1 between psychological well-being (DASS-21) and socioeconomic status (FAS), a test of normality was conducted initially to check for skewness. Examination of the normality assumptions revealed that the distribution of both DASS-21 (significant positive Skewness = .632; Kurtosis= .117) and FAS scores (positive Skewness = .104; Kurtosis= .117) deviated significantly from a normal distribution. Additionally, the Shapiro-Wilk tests generated a statistically significant departure from normality for DASS-21 ($p=0.010$); however, the FAS displayed a non-significant departure from normality ($p=0.057$), denoting a reasonably normal distribution.

Initially, linear regression was planned to test the study hypotheses. Taking into account that one of the combined scales deviated from the normal distribution, violating the assumptions required for parametric testing. Consequently, non-parametric alternatives were employed. Taking this into account, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to examine the nature and significance of the relationship between SES, measured by the FAS scale, and PW, measured by the DASS-21. The results indicated that there was a non-significant negative correlation between the two variables, $r(95) = -.19, p = .067$

Table 1 : Pairwise Comparisons of Classes of Income

	Sample 1- Sample 2	Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
Depression	High Income Class-low Income Class Low	9.697	.159	.478
	High Income Class-Middle Income Class	20.967	.004	.011
	Low Income Class-Middle Income Class	-11.270	.102	.305
Anxiety	High Income Class-low Income Class	10.760	.118	.354
	High Income Class-Middle Income Class	17.500	.016	.047
	Low Income Class-Middle Income Class	-6.740	.328	.983
Stress	High Income Class-low Income Class Low	10.076	.144	.431
	High Income Class-Middle Income Class	22.817	.002	.005
	Low Income Class-Middle Income Class	-12.741	.064	.193

Note: Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same. Asymptotic significance (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is .050. Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Effects of socioeconomic status on psychological well-being

Initially, multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was planned to test the study hypotheses. However, the DASS-21 scores deviated significantly from a normal distribution, violating the assumptions required for parametric testing. Consequently, a

non-parametric alternative was adopted. Since the outcome variable violated normality assumptions, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed to examine differences in depression, anxiety, and stress scores across income categories. Kruskal-Wallis test yielded significant findings for depression ($H = 8.407, df = 2, p = 0.015$) and stress ($H = 9.986, df = 2, p = 0.007$) and demonstrated partial significance for

anxiety ($H= 5.966$, $df =2$, $p = 0.051$) across categories of classes of income.

Subsequently, Post hoc analyses using the Bonferroni correction were conducted to identify which specific SES groups showed significant differences in scores for depression, anxiety, and stress.

Additionally, descriptive analysis was carried out to ascertain which of the two categories (high-income classes or middle-income classes) had the greatest number of PW issues. The analysis's findings were shown graphically using a bar chart (see Figure 4), which showed that,

when compared to the low and high-income classes, the middle-income class showed higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. Therefore, the second hypothesis, that university students from lower socioeconomic classes face greater psychological impact was rejected.

Figure 4 : *Distribution of Depression, Anxiety and Stress across Different Classes of Income*

Discussion

The primary aim of this research was to examine the relationship between SES and PW among university students in Sri Lanka and to determine which SES group experienced greater psychological impact during an economic crisis. The results demonstrated that there was a non-significant negative correlation between SES and PW. In addition to those findings, the study also found that university students belonging to the middle SES had lower PW, reflected by higher levels of depression, anxiety, and stress during the economic crisis.

The study's results revealed a non-significant negative relationship between SES and PW among university students in Sri Lanka, leading to the rejection of the study's proposed hypothesis. This suggests that the relationship between the two variables may be more intricate than previously assumed, and that factors other than SES might have contributed to determining students' well-being. The economic crisis could have contributed to several factors that eventually influenced the PW of university students, such as increased class sizes implemented by universities to reduce costs,

fewer academic options, decreased student support services, and reduced part-time employment opportunities due to the competitive job market. These factors may have negatively affected students' prospects of finding full-time employment after graduation.

These economic challenges, along with common sources of stress such as academic stress, social relationships (including family expectations, romantic relationships, and peer relationships), involvement in student political activities and conflicts within the campus environment, and living conditions in university hostels, could have influenced one another intricately, resulting in harmful psychological consequences among Sri Lankan students (Mahees, 2020). Additionally, the FAS's reduced-scale reliability may have led to unexpected outcomes that did not support the study's first hypothesis. The reduced reliability could be explained through response bias related to social desirability associated with online surveys (Angel et al., 2019), where participants may not have responded honestly about their family's economic standing.

The present study's findings correspond with Cook (2014) study, which similarly reported a non-significant negative relationship between SES and PW among university students. Similar to the current study, Cook (2014) also employed the DASS-21 scale to measure PW and grouped participants into three SES (lower, middle, and upper), with a participant size of 95 participants. Cook (2014) justified that many students were reluctant to disclose their family's financial status and that the scale contained textual errors and language ambiguities, which may have contributed to the unexpected findings. Additionally, Cook's study also administered surveys for data gathering, which may have increased the possibility of social desirability

bias. These factors may have played a role in the surprising findings, underscoring the need for careful consideration of the methodological constraints when analysing the results.

Further, findings from Sakshi and Baloria (2023) and Wang and Geng (2019) also aligned with the current study; however, these studies were carried out among different groups, including university lecturers and respondents from the Chinese General Social Survey, respectively.

The second finding of the study indicated that Sri Lankan university students belonging to the middle SES experienced greater levels of depression, anxiety, and stress during the economic crisis, thereby rejecting the study's proposed second hypothesis. These unforeseen outcomes question the conventional framework of social selection theory. This theory argues that individuals vulnerable to mental disorders have a greater likelihood of falling into lower socioeconomic positions as a result of their condition (Jin et al., 2020), indicating that lower SES is linked to increased PW distress. However, the present study findings imply that this relationship may not apply universally and that the middle-class population, which is often regarded as socially and economically advantaged, may not be immune to mental health concerns, especially during a period of economic crisis.

Although the results differ from the proposed hypothesis, it can be reasonably assumed that the middle SES was the most impacted group during the economic downturn. This is because high SES individuals possess accumulated wealth and resources that function as a financial buffer, whilst low-income groups frequently receive government aid (Jayathilaka et al., 2022) and have prior experience dealing with financial challenges. However, the middle SES group

might not possess the financial capacity of the wealthy or receive the level of government assistance available to the low SES group, leaving them more vulnerable during economic crises.

Additionally, middle-SES individuals are primarily reliant on income through employment. During the economic crisis, these individuals may have experienced job loss and increased job instability, exposing them to a higher risk of unemployment and a reduction in income (Szymańska, 2019). Furthermore, the Sri Lankan government implemented a new income taxation policy that heavily impacted the middle SES due to reductions in income thresholds, making it significantly difficult for them to fulfil their financial obligations (Shanthaarchch, 2022), including their reduced ability to support their children's educational pursuits. As a result, middle-class students may have had to take up part-time employment and even consider borrowing loans to fund their studies (Shanthaarchch, 2022).

An alternate explanation for the present study to obtain these results is due to the greater importance placed on educational attainment by middle SES students. Azaria et al. (2019) noted that middle-SES students have a stronger inclination to pursue higher education, outperforming both their low-SES and high-SES counterparts. This is because students from low SES classes may face financial constraints that make it challenging for them to continue their education, potentially causing them to consider discontinuing from education or prioritising job search. Students from wealthier households, on the other hand, may be less driven to pursue advanced qualifications due to their existing high SES level (Azaria et al., 2019). Middle SES students attach greater importance to educational attainment, particularly during times of

economic distress, viewing education as a tool to improve living standards (Varghese, 2001). However, this commitment to completing their education amidst financial and economic stressors might have inadvertently resulted in lower PW in middle SES students, as demonstrated by the study findings.

The current study findings align with Agberotimi's (2020) study, which was conducted among healthcare personnel and the general public during COVID-19. The Nigerian study found no statistically significant results for stress or anxiety, but it did find that individuals in the standard (middle) income class had greater levels of depression. The results were ascribed to the fact that the middle SES, which in Nigeria makes up the majority of entrepreneurs and higher-income employees in the private and public sectors, represents the largest proportion of the population. Due to large scale layoffs, reduced pay, and reduction in income brought on by the COVID-19 crisis, the middle SES members were especially vulnerable to financial difficulties, which were further aggravated by the effects of lockdowns (Agberotimi et al., 2020). While the economic crisis and COVID-19 were distinct events, both situations had similar underlying effects, including economic instability and decline in income, which likely contributed to higher prevalence of depression reported among middle SES groups. Although the present study findings align with previous research among health workers, it is crucial to note that studies pertaining to middle SES are very limited in the existing literature on SES and PW among university students.

Limitations & Implications

Every research study is restricted by certain limitations, and the current study is not an exception. Firstly, the study employed

self-report measures, which might have included unreliable responses, such as those caused by social desirability bias. Secondly, the study could not achieve the required statistical power value for the sample size, restricting generalisability of the findings to a larger population. Thirdly, low reliability scores of the FAS might have had an impact on the accuracy of the study findings. Fourthly, the limited availability of published non-significant findings on this topic presented challenges in interpreting results in relation to prior research. Finally, the absence of a validated Sri Lankan SES questionnaire, and the determination of participants' SES based only on their income levels, was seen as another limitation of the study.

Despite these limitations, the study provided meaningful insights into the complex relationship between SES and PW. While some studies have found a significant relationship between the two variables, the present study's findings challenge assumptions about the consistency and reliability of this relationship. In addition, it is important to note that many studies with non-significant results go unpublished due to selective publication bias, which may skew the research evidence on a subject and produce a fragmented understanding of the topic (Nair, 2019). These unpublished studies could provide insightful data even if their results are not statistically significant.

The current study serves as an illustration of this; even though it demonstrated a non-significant negative relationship between the two variables, it did reveal that middle-SES university students are psychologically impacted more than low and high-SES students. In light of the study, the significance of publishing non-significant results becomes evident. This not only contributes to a more holistic understanding of the topic, but it also prevents

repetition of research efforts and aids in refining hypotheses and guiding subsequent research investigations in an evidence-based direction (Nair, 2019). Thus, the study emphasises the need to encourage transparency in research by acknowledging and publishing non-significant findings to enhance academic literature.

Furthermore, previous studies report diverse findings pertaining to the relationship between SES and PW among university students; however, there is a considerable variation in the findings reported. For example, some studies propose that university students from lower SES have higher PW problems (Mohammad et al., 2020; Wahed & Hassan, 2017), whereas others argue that students from higher SES have greater PW-related difficulties (Ismail & Shujaat, 2018; Salami & Walker, 2014). The current study, which observed higher PW problems among middle SES, adds to the existing literature base by drawing attention to another aspect of the multifaceted SES-PW relationship, as research focusing on this target population is very limited. This variation underscores the importance of incorporating different SES groups when formulating interventions to address PW concerns among university students.

Future Research Recommendation

The present study not only yields valuable insights but also provides a basis for subsequent research. A qualitative approach could be used to supplement this quantitative study in future research by exploring key stressors such as academic stress, financial strain, and job insecurity, that might influence the PW of university students from middle SES families during the crisis, providing comprehensive understanding of these issues. Additionally, increasing the sample size and enhancing scale's reliability would provide a more robust framework for future studies. Further, while

determining SES, additional factors such as education and occupation should be considered, as these variables might contribute to a more thorough SES assessment. Furthermore, a comparative analysis between middle SES students from public and private universities might help to better understand whether contextual factors have an influence on the decline of PW among university students. Finally, future research should highlight the importance of publishing non-significant findings, as this assists in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the topic and enhancing scholarly discourse.

Conclusion

PW among university students is a widespread concern, and in the light of Sri Lanka's economic crisis, no student is entirely exempted from these challenges, regardless of which SES group they belong to. Therefore, the current study investigated the relationship between PW and SES among university students and examined which SES group experienced higher PW issues during the economic crisis in Sri Lanka. The study found a non-significant negative relationship between SES and PW but indicated that university students belonging to middle SES had higher PW problems. Although the study yielded a non-significant negative relationship between SES and PW, the findings do offer some insight into how the relationship between the two variables may be complex and multifaceted, which may reconsider previous assumptions. Additionally, the study provides meaningful insights into the challenges university students experience concerning PW during an economic crisis. Lastly, the research serves as an important reminder to educators and related organisations that students from all SES levels, not just those who are traditionally considered at risk, may experience PW issues.

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